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About "Ethnography" in the Literature Review in the Study of New Media

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ABSTRACT

In the research of journalism and communication, the introduction of ethnography makes the research problems in journalism and communication become more and more clear. As media technologies such as the Internet are deeply interwoven with society, the impact of new media on human society is becoming more and more significant, and the field of new media has naturally become an important area of concern for news and communication. Research topics on new media are increasingly rich. At the same time, ethnography, as a research method, has become a non-negligible way to understand news communication, especially new media research. This article selects the literature in domestic journals between 2000 and 2019 as the research object, through literature search of ethnographic research methods in the study of new media with 39 references, carries on the statistical analysis to make a research on "ethnography" in new media in the literature review, and summed up the "ethnography" in the study of new media use of four kinds of ways.

INTRODUCTION

With the emergence and popularization of the Internet, new media can be seen everywhere. The research of ethnography is not only limited to the traditional research field -- the field. Meanwhile, the virtual space of new media, with the Internet as the main technical means and new media as the carrier, has also become an important field of ethnography method research.

In order to understand the ethnographic research methods in the study of new media and the application effect, the author in domestic journals between 2000 and 2019 studies of journalism and communication, the international press, "the news university", "the news", "Nanjing social science", "social", sociological research, and Hong Kong and Taiwan journal in the journal of communication and social, "journalism" as the research object, a total of 39 collect related theses, and statistical analysis.

LITERATURE

Ethnography is an explanatory research method, which has been fully developed and applied in the research of anthropology. Recently, ethnography has been introduced into the study of journalism and communication. Ethnography originates from anthropologists' investigation of some cultural phenomena. (Yumei, 2012) academic circles generally believe that participatory observation is one of the most important content of in ethnographic research, the researchers for its research object, the object of study in general is given priority to with cultural attributes) field investigation, to continuously go deep into the research objects of daily life, in a long time immersion involved in or "interview" way to collect data, through the observation of the object of study of daily life, get the related data, then carries on the comparison to these data, analysis, in order to get the basic concept of this culture. Ethnographic research and main research object of cultural attribute, this nature determines the methods must demand the researchers into the objects of daily life, and with the

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formation of a good relationship, for using the ethnography method to study scholars, they have the dual role for researchers and observation of the participants.

In traditional ethnography study, its practice is concentrated in the field with the reality of ethnic cultural practice field, with the development of media technology, new media technology, the Internet to connect the world, new media become another important human activities together "location", therefore, the researchers of ethnography "to write" the natural also get the corresponding development of the field. The research field in reality and the "virtual field" created by new media technology are intertwined. (Xinru, 2004) It has become an important reality of ethnography research, and also provides more possibilities for the improvement and development of ethnography research. (Xinyuan, 2018) Guo Jianbin is one of the earliest scholars who applied ethnography in communication studies in China, and his research achievements are of his own. He has made great contributions in introducing ethnography methods to China. In the field of communication studies, ethnographic research methods have been widely used in interpersonal communication, mass communication, cultural communication, etc. The reason is that "the design of qualitative research strategies such as ethnography is mainly to understand the orientation of natural scenes and their main activity characteristics. The power of these paths lies in their ability to provide a "contextualized" understanding of the connections between different aspects of the object of study. today, with the universal use of new media, new media's influence on people's social life values are also increasingly prominent, and therefore, the new media and its derivative of social cultural phenomenon increasingly attract the attention of social science researchers, as is shouldering the important mission of science, culture and anthropology also special attention to the new media, naturally, the most representative of anthropological ethnography research methods focus on new media research.

Statistics of relevant literature on "ethnography" in new media research

Literature statistics of major journals

By sorting out the literature in the journal Journalism and Communication Research (eliminating the literature collection method of keyword thematic search and adopting the judgment of method use for each article), a total of 10 articles have been sorted out to study new media with the method or orientation of "ethnography" research. The first article published in this journal to study new media with ethnography research method is a case analysis made by Ding Wei, trying to explore the relationship between new media technology and the social relationship between migrant workers by using ethnography research method.

With the method of literature collection mentioned above, a total of 6 articles have been sorted out in international Media to conduct research on new media with the method or orientation of "ethnography".

With the method of literature collection mentioned above, a total of 10 articles have been sorted out in Journalism University to conduct research on new media with the method or orientation of "ethnography" research.

With the method of literature collection mentioned above, the Journal of Communication and Society and The Journal of Journalism research have sorted out a total of 9 articles that use the research method or orientation of "ethnography" to study new media. Among them, "Journal of Communication and Society" accounts for 6, "Journalism research" accounts for 3.

With the method of literature collection mentioned above, four articles have been sorted out in Society, Sociological Research, Nanjing Social Science and Journalist to conduct research on new media with the method or orientation of "ethnography" research, one of which is in each journal.

A total of 39 articles were collected and counted from the research methods or orientation of ethnography in the above journals on new media. Among them, there are 10 articles in Journalism and Communication Research, 6 articles in International Press, 1 article in Journalist, 10 articles in

Journalism University, 1 article in Nanjing Social Science, 1 article in Society and 1 article in Sociology Research, 6 articles in Journal of Communication and Society, and 3 articles in Journalism research.

(A few notes on literature collection methods; 1. Discard the literature collection practice of keyword thematic search and use the judgment of method use for each article; Data collection for keyword searches may include non-new media research articles in the statistical scope, while some articles that do not clearly explain the research methods may be omitted. 2. Periodical classification statistics are adopted instead of the so-called full database search) statistics the change trend of the number of articles in the field of new media research using the research methods or orientations of "ethnography" from 2000 to 2019. Such articles generally show an increasing trend, which fully indicates that the research methods or orientations of "ethnography" have been greatly applied in the field of new media research.

Research status of ethnography in new media research

(I) The categories of the application ways of "ethnography" in new media research

The author preliminarily classifies the research methods adopted in the 39 articles collected, and now divides the existing application methods of "ethnography" in new media research into four types:

Type I: a single properties of ethnographic research field, this type of well inherited methods of ethnographic research of anthropology, in the practical field investigation points, the participatory observation as one of the core content of this system, such as reading, not the flow of the home: a case study of new media technology and rural migrant workers in social relations with the method of ethnography, to experience the in-depth interviews and individual or group is given priority to, to live in shenzhen sheckhard village of human county cadastral taxi drivers use of media technology including car phone, mobile phones, the Internet as a case from one side to show the structure of the migrant workers social relations pattern and its evolution process. (Xinru, 2017) this type of approach can be summarized as the investigation of the use of new media by a certain group in order to explore the impact of the use of new media on human society. According to the statistics of existing texts, a total of 10 literatures can be classified into type I.

Type II: An ethnographic type that combines online observation with offline interview. This type of method combines the characteristics of online observation of virtual ethnography with the methods of field interview or participant observation of ethnography in the sense of anthropology, such as Wang Xinyuan's Online Communities in Mobile Life: China's new generation of rural migrants social media use of anthropology research, by the method of anthropological ethnography, combined online, through to the new generation of rural migrants use of social media participatory observation, field observation to access the object of study at the same time, in order to explore how the new generation of rural construction community identity "flow" of daily life, at the same time, the new mode of interpersonal communication is how to form in the use of social media. Four ways of this type can be summed up in the online inspection at the same time, focus on new media constructed by the "new space", and at the same time pay attention to the on-the-spot investigation object living space, online and offline Spaces are intertwined, and in order to reach to come into contact with the object of study is the most real life state, to achieve with the perspective of the research object to writing ethnography. Of course, for the 16 articles to be divided into this category, the authors adopt the method of Type II to study the research objects. The methods are consistent, but may be limited by various reasons, and the writing depth of ethnography may be different. According to the statistics of existing texts, a total of 16 literatures can be classified into type II.

Type III: An analysis of the methodology used by "ethnography" in the study of new media. Articles of this type mostly discuss the rationality of adopting ethnography research method in the study of new media from the perspective of methodology, and summarize the experience of ethnography method in the study of new media from research cases. For example, Bu Yumei's Fictitious Ethnography: Fields, Methods and Ethics; "Into the Virtual Field" by Zhu Lingfei and Sun Xinru extends the field points of ethnography investigation. The "new space" created by the Internet is also the site of new field investigation. Meanwhile, some scholars have summarized various methods and attention

requirements for Internet ethnography. 5The discussion of ethnography and network ethnography should not be limited to the method level, but should be compared with new questions and new answers." 6 In addition, some scholars have conducted a comprehensive discussion on the principles and relevant scope of Internet ethnography, and clarified some misunderstandings and misunderstandings about Internet ethnography. According to the statistics of existing texts, a total of 7 literatures can be classified into type III.

Type IV: "pure" online network ethnographic research, the use of this type of "ethnography" way, mainly focused on the investigation object to use the "new media" create a "new" space, the main body relationship exists in the space of all kinds of paint, explains the building of the new type of space mechanism and information communication mechanism between the main body, or reveal the "new" space and realistic space. For example, Huzen's "Building Community and Manufacturing Pleasure: Types and Significance of Fans' Communication Practice in Online Communities" divides fans' communication practice in online communities into four types through continuous observation of online communities, and finds that fans' communication practice is closely related to the construction and maintenance of online communities. According to the statistics of existing texts, a total of 5 literatures can be classified into type IV.

According to the statistical data, the number of articles of type 2 is the largest, accounting for 16 articles, accounting for 41%; the number of articles of type 1 is 10, accounting for 26%; the number of articles of type 3 is 8, accounting for 20%; and the number of articles of type IV is 5, accounting for 13%. It reflects that "ethnography" is mostly used in the study of new media through the combination of online and offline methods. Meanwhile, the traditional ethnography research method is also one of the important ways to study new media.

Summary and Discussion

Through the study of some representative for carding and analysis, we can further clear national aim at veins in the study of new media, we can be roughly divided into four types of use: 1, the use of a single traditional ethnography 2, the combination of online and offline ethnography 3, theoretical discussion on the use of the new media in the national 4, single line network ethnography. Through sorting out, we can find that the academic circle of journalism and communication has made substantial achievements in the application of ethnographic research methods, especially in the study of new media, which creatively USES a research method of "network ethnography". At the same time, as a research method, ethnography also has some problems in the study of new media. There is a relative lack of research on ethnography in the study of new media.

Compared with the traditional anthropological ethnography, the research on ethnography in new media is at the initial stage and progress is slow. Ethnography method used in the study of new media is using traditional ethnography directly grafting, there is no innovation, only the traditional ethnography method research in the field of grafting of the new media environment or the actual research field to focus on new media have created a virtual space, some research but also practical research field and new media created by combining space; Ethnographic research methods require long-term observation of the research objects, participation in the research by observing "cultural" research behavior, and recording research materials closely related to the research issues. Only in this way can ethnographic research reach the level of detailed ethnographic writing. (Xinru, 2016) in the study of ethnography in new media, the writing of "ethnography" is often superficial and fails to deeply reveal the internal logic of research issues; In the existing ethnographic studies, researchers often focus on the various activities of the research objects in the "virtual space" created by new media, but pay little attention to the actual offline interaction behavior and the influence of the online "virtual space" behavior on the offline. The application of ethnography as a research method in new media research expands researchers' cognitive path to research problems. (Rongchun, 2008) it enriches the research content of new media research and should be paid attention and attention by the academic circle. Meanwhile, problems arising from the application of ethnography in new media research should not be ignored.

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